

IMPACT OF *AZOTOBACTER CHROOCOCCUM* KO2020 ON THE MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF SOME COTTON (*GOSSYPIUM HIRSUTUM* L.) VARIETIES

¹Gulirukh H. ²Bakhromova, ³Mohichehra A. ⁴Pattaeva, ⁵Bakhtiyor A. ⁶Rasulov
Institute of Genetics and Plant Experimental Biology, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences,
111226, Kybray District, Tashkent Province, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14049926>

The application of *Azotobacter* species as biofertilizers in cotton cultivation has been widely studied due to their ability to promote plant growth and improve yield-related traits. *Azotobacter* is known for its nitrogen-fixing capabilities, producing bioavailable nitrogen for plants. This feature is especially valuable in cotton, a crop with high nutrient demands, as *Azotobacter* reduces the need for synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, making cotton production more sustainable (Rana et al., 2016).

Several studies have highlighted the positive morphological changes in cotton due to *Azotobacter* application. For example, *Azotobacter chroococcum* has been observed to enhance root and shoot growth by producing phytohormones like auxins, gibberellins, and cytokinins, which stimulate cell division and elongation (Desai et al., 2012). Treated cotton plants generally show increased plant height, leaf area, and overall biomass, leading to enhanced photosynthetic activity and better nutrient uptake (Khan et al., 2014).

Furthermore, cotton treated with *Azotobacter* often demonstrates improved reproductive traits, such as an increased number of pods per plant, higher boll weight, and enhanced fiber quality. This can be attributed not only to the enhanced nitrogen supply but also to the bacterium's ability to improve soil structure and microbial diversity, creating a more favorable rhizosphere environment (Gholami et al., 2013).

The aim of current research was to evaluate impact of nitrogen fixing bacterial strain *Azotobacter chroococcum* K2020 on some cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) varieties, such as “Buxoro-102”, “O`zFA-710”, “O`zFA-709” and “Gulbahor-2”.

Table. Impact of *A. chroococcum* KO2020 on cotton varieties morphological traits (cm)

№	Varieties	Number of	Control						Experiment					
			Plant height			Boll number			Plant height			Boll number		
			X ±m	σ	v	X ±m	σ	v	X ±m	σ	v	X ±m	σ	v
1	Gulbahor-2	40	125,75±0, 96	7,12	5,66	22,35±0,2 1	3,90	17,44	139,00±0, 81	7,15	5,15	30,45± 0,60	3,97	13,03
2	Buxoro-102	40	92,40±0,7 6	7,74	8,38	20,52±0,34	6,15	29,96	105,25±1, 22	6,80	6,46	24,70± 0,40	2,64	10,68

3	O`zFA-710	40	101,90±0, 84	10,64	10,44	19,22±0,24	3,71	22,06	117,55±1, 44	7,65	6,51	24,90± 0,71	4,70	18,88
4	O`zFA-709	40	122,00±1, 70	12,29	10,07	22,97±0,17	5,18	22,54	130,30±1, 61	7,15	5,48	30,30± 0,92	6,10	20,12

The results demonstrate that among the cotton varieties inoculated with *A. chroococcum* KO2020, the "Gulbahor-2" variety displayed a statistically significant increase in plant height, with the experimental group achieving an average of 13.25 cm greater height than the control group (Table). Enhanced morphological responses to *A. chroococcum* KO2020 were recorded across all assessed traits in the four cotton varieties compared to controls. In particular, "Gulbahor-2" and "UzFA-709" exhibited the highest pod counts under the treatment, with mean pod numbers of 30.45 ± 0.60 and 30.30 ± 0.92 , respectively, indicating an improved yield potential associated with the bacterial inoculation. It can be concluded that *A. chroococcum* KO2020 positively impacted on cotton morphological traits.

REFERENCES

- Desai, S., Praveen Kumar, G., & Sultana, U. (2012). *Azotobacter* as a biofertilizer and its effect on growth of plants. *International Journal of Applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology*, 3(1), 83–88.
- Gholami, A., Biyari, A., Gholipoor, M., & Rahmani, H. A. (2013). Growth promotion of maize and cotton by *Azotobacter* inoculation. *Agriculture and Forestry*, 59(1), 19–27.
- Khan, M. S., Zaidi, A., & Wani, P. A. (2014). Role of *Azotobacter* in sustainable agriculture. In *Microbial Strategies for Crop Improvement* (pp. 23–37). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Rana, M. S., Kumawat, S. M., & Bhatt, R. K. (2016). Effect of biofertilizers on growth and productivity of cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 4(6), 170–175.